

Recommendations for a fair and well Doncaster

Easy
Read

Introduction

Fairness & Wellbeing
Commission

This information is from
Doncaster's **Fairness and
Wellbeing Commission**

A **Commission** is a group of
people trusted by a government
or someone in charge, to do
something.

The **Fairness and Wellbeing
Commission** has looked at the
challenges people in Doncaster
might have.

The Commission has come up
with some advice for places in
Doncaster (called
'**recommendations**') on how we
can make Doncaster more fair.

What are the 'recommendations'?

Theme 1: Creating a Fair and Empowering future

The Fairness and Wellbeing Commission wants to create a **'Fair and Empowering future'** for people in Doncaster.

'Empowering' means people having control over their own lives.

To help make a **'fair and empowering future'** there are some recommendations from the commission.

Recommendation 1

Education places in Doncaster settings should **support young people** with:

- a feeling of **belonging** to where you live

- **skills** that they can use for life

Recommendation 2

Young people in Doncaster should have **equal education**.

This means that everyone gets the support they may need to do just as good as anyone else.

Recommendation 3

Children and young people should have a say in:

- the **support** they get

- the **decisions** that effect them.

Recommendation 4

Young people should have help to find **work** after they have finished school

Theme 2: Help to Navigate Life's Tipping Points

Sometimes we can have big changes in our life, we call these '**tipping points**'

Sometimes '**tipping points**' can be tough on our minds.

The **commission** recommends that places in Doncaster should help people with these **big changes** in their life.

Recommendation 5

Use **evidence** to support people at hard times in their lives.

This means that support should be based on what we know **works**.

Recommendation 6

Create **strong communities** by:

- Having places you can find support **locally**

- Making sure everybody knows their **legal rights**

Recommendation 7

Have **trusted support** in Doncaster communities

This means that people can reply on this support to be there for them if they need it.

Recommendation 8

People have **safe and healthy** homes to keep them well in Doncaster

Theme 3: Tackling In-Work Poverty

Sometimes people can have a job but still not have enough **money** to live well.

This is called '**in-work poverty**'.

The **commission** recommends that we should make sure people have enough **money and support** when they are working.

Recommendation 9

We should help people by:

- Working to stop **'in- work poverty'**

- helping people to have **reliable jobs.**

Recommendation 10

Businesses should be **responsible** to their **community**.

Recommendation 11

Support people to achieve **social mobility**.

Social Mobility is about how easy it is for people to change their place in society, for example to get a good job.

Recommendation 12

Make **job opportunities better** in Doncaster.

Giving everyone a fair chance to **do well** and **develop**.

Theme 4: Ensuring Equitable Access for All

This means that everyone should be able to have access to the same **opportunities**.

Recommendation 13

Create trusted Community Support Hubs to help keep people healthy and well.

Recommendation 14

Be Kind and Compassionate when supporting people.

Recommendation 15

Support people in Doncaster residents to use digital technology.

Recommendation 16

Make Doncaster's Public Transport accessible to all.